

ROLE OF X-RAY IMAGING IN DETERMINING STRUCTURAL AND FUNCTIONAL ALTERATIONS IN THE GASTROINTESTINAL TRACT FOLLOWING BARIATRIC PROCEDURES

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Abstract. Bariatric surgery is recognized as the most effective method for treating morbid obesity, ensuring long-term weight loss and remission of comorbid diseases. In Uzbekistan, the number of bariatric surgeries has increased more than 10 times over the past decade, reaching 5,000 operations per year by 2026. The most common bariatric interventions are laparoscopic longitudinal gastric resection (sleeve gastrectomy, SG) and gastric bypass (GB), which constitute over 80% of all operations [4]. These interventions lead to cardinal changes in the anatomy and physiology of the gastrointestinal tract, requiring long-term monitoring.

Keywords: multispiral computed tomography, bariatric surgery, postoperative complications, structural and functional changes, gastrointestinal tract, obesity, sleeve gastrectomy, gastric shunting

Purpose of the study: to assess the diagnostic capabilities of radiological methods in identifying and monitoring structural and functional restructuring of the gastrointestinal tract in the postoperative period of bariatric interventions.

The study included 86 patients who underwent bariatric surgeries from January 2022 to December 2026, of which sleeve gastrectomy was performed in 47 patients (54.7%), gastric bypass - in 39 patients (45.3%). Demographic characteristics: age 18-65 years (average 42.3 ± 11.2 years), women 65 (75.6%), men 21 (24.4%), initial BMI 35-58 kg/m² (average 43.8 ± 6.4 kg/m²). Dynamic observation was conducted: after 1 month in 86 patients, 6 months in 80, 12 months in 69, 24 months in 54, 36 months in 31 patients.

Radiological diagnostics of structural and functional changes after bariatric surgeries is a complex of radiation research methods aimed at identifying and monitoring anatomical and physiological restructuring of the gastrointestinal tract in patients with morbid obesity in the postoperative period. The diagnostic program is based on the use of various radiological techniques using contrast agents to visualize the altered anatomy of the gastrointestinal tract. The study was conducted on patients after the most common bariatric interventions: laparoscopic longitudinal gastric resection (sleeve gastrectomy) and gastric bypass, performed at various stages of the postoperative period. Typical methodological approaches: Stage-by-stage radiological examination involves visual radiography of the abdominal organs in vertical and horizontal positions to detect free gas, diagnose intestinal obstruction, and assess the position of surgical materials. Contrast radiography is performed differentially: in the first 3 days, a water-soluble contrast agent (urographin, gastrographin) is used, after a month and later - barium sulfate 100-150 ml. The study is carried out in stages: assessing the initial condition on an empty stomach, taking the first dose of contrast (20-30 ml), polypositional examination, additional doses of contrast (20-30 ml), functional tests. If intestinal transit is suspected, barium passage is performed through the small intestine, taking 200-300 ml of barium suspension, and X-rays are taken after 1, 2, 4, 6 hours until the contrast agent reaches the cecum.

CONCLUSION: Thus, radiological methods demonstrate high diagnostic effectiveness in identifying complications of bariatric surgeries: anastomotic failure (sensitivity 94.2%), stenosis (89.7%), reflux (92.3%). Specific patterns of structural and functional restructuring have been identified: compensatory intestinal dilatation after GB, adaptive dilation of the gastric tube after SG after 12-18 months. Radiological predictors of surgical failure have been established: stomach tube dilation >6 cm correlates with weight recurrence ($r=0.73$) and the need for revision. Radioscopy retains unique advantages in functional diagnostics, providing real-time assessment of evacuatory function and peristalsis. The economic efficiency and accessibility of radiological methods make them optimal for routine monitoring of patients after bariatric surgeries.

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